

Australian Research Data Commons

Impact Case Study

TEMPLATE FOR SHOWCASING IMPACT THROUGH A CASE STUDY

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What is this template for?

This template helps you present your research project to people who make decisions about research funding. It focuses on your project's success at overcoming data/ analysis challenges and the impact of your project through a case study. Use this template when there are measurements of impact to share. These case studies are published on the RDC webpages.

How to use this template

1. Replace the italicised prompt text with your own words.
2. Keep it as simple as possible, avoid technical jargon if possible.
3. Modify the template to suit your context.
4. Pages 2 -3 are worked examples
5. Test your case study! Consider obtaining feedback from those who are unfamiliar with the topic.

Case Study: *Add your topic here*

1. RESEARCH TOPIC DESCRIPTION
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● <i>Describe your research topic in 1-2 sentences.</i>
2. THE DATA/ANALYSIS CHALLENGE
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● <i>Provide 1-2 sentences explaining what the data or analysis challenge is.</i>● <i>Include data, facts, figures of the challenge, if possible.</i>
3. THE APPROACH/METHODOLOGY
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● <i>Describe the approach/ methods.</i>
4. WHAT EXPERTISE WAS HELPFUL?
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● <i>Describe the expertise which helped shape your research.</i><ul style="list-style-type: none">○ <i>Which resources helped provide direction?</i>○ <i>Whose expertise did you lean in to?</i>
5. THE IMPACT
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● <i>Outline the outcome, including unexpected outcomes, if any.</i>● <i>Evidence to support that this outcome happened</i>● <i>Other use cases, how/ where else else might the approach be applied?</i>

EXAMPLE ONLY

(Read the [published case study](#))

Case Study: Social Media Analysis Reveals That Most People Have No Idea What Autism Is

1. RESEARCH TOPIC DESCRIPTION

- *Describe your research topic in 1-2 sentences.*

The aim was to better understand the experiences and perspectives of autistic people in relation to autism disclosure. The research question was, “what are people saying online about autism disclosure?”

2. THE DATA/ANALYSIS CHALLENGE

- *Provide 1-2 sentences explaining what the data or analysis challenge is.*
- *Include data, figures and anecdotes about the challenge, if possible.*

Dr Chris Edwards, a research fellow at the [Aspect Research Centre for Autism Practice \(ARCAP\)](#), led the research. ARCAP is the research arm of Aspect. “Our research question was: what are people saying [online] about autism disclosure?”, said Dr Edwards. “Rather than recruiting research participants and asking them questions we wanted answered, we looked at what people were saying online in those natural conversations and posts.”

3. THE APPROACH/METHODOLOGY

- *Describe the approach/ methods.*

Rather than using traditional methods of interviews and surveys to collect data, the researchers turned to social media, qualitatively analysing 3 years of disclosure-related posts on Twitter/X and Reddit, sourced via the ARDC-supported [Australian Digital Observatory](#). Autism researchers have been turning to social media for data on identification and diagnosis, aloneness and connectedness, identity, burnout, and vaccine controversy. But this is the first time that social media data has been used to explore autism disclosure.

Social media data has many advantages over data collected through traditional research methods where the researchers frame the questions, risking some bias. Data from social media may be more inclusive of members of the autistic community who are more comfortable communicating online and may not seek out opportunities to participate in research. The data on Twitter/X and Reddit is also public, it’s longitudinal, it’s international, and it incorporates the perspectives and experiences not only of autistic people but of their family members, friends and carers. It’s also dynamic, continually being added to.

4. WHAT EXPERTISE WAS HELPFUL?

- *Which resources helped provide direction?*
- *Whose expertise did you lean in to?*
- *How did you get the leads to who/ what might help you?*

Getting hold of the data in a form that could be imported into research software NVivo for analysis required expertise, which drew Dr Edwards to the [Australian Digital Observatory](#). “I tried several ways to pull social media data from the platforms, including NCapture [a browser add-in that captures web content for importing to NVivo], thinking it would be easy, before coming to the conclusion that I needed help”, he said.

The Australian Digital Observatory is national research infrastructure for accessing and analysing dynamic human data on the web, including existing collections of national interest across Twitter, Flickr, YouTube, Reddit, Instagram, and gaming platforms such as Steam. “The QUT Digital Observatory team had really clear information about what they could do and how they could help”, said Dr Edwards. “We gave them some search terms and shortly afterwards received a sample of the data so we could check the volume and relevance before pulling the entire database together. “ The Australian Digital Observatory provided the data in a form that Dr Edwards could import directly into NVivo for analysis. “It was a really smooth and easy process, and I want to do it again the next time we have an interest in something social-media-related.”

5. THE IMPACT

- *Outline the outcome, including unexpected outcomes, if any.*
- *Evidence to support that this outcome happened*
- *Other use cases , how/ where else else might the approach be applied?*

Creating a society where autistic people can feel safe to disclose, if they want to, is a challenge. The researchers suggest that we need to make this everyone’s responsibility, while respecting the confidentiality of disclosures, shifting the emotional burden of disclosure from ‘them’ to ‘us’, and reducing the spread of misinformation. “It’s really going to be a slow and gradual process for society”, said Dr Edwards. “But I think this [research] adds to that process, particularly by including people who may not traditionally be included in autism research. “And if you reflect on society over the past few years, I think you can see how things are slowly changing. The media is still a problem, [but] there are slowly becoming better autistic portrayals in TV shows and autism voices in the news.”

- End -